

Plant Disease Detection on Multispectral Images using Vision Transformers *

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Abstract

Precise identification of plant diseases facilitates effective agricultural management. However, classifying plant diseases poses formidable challenges due to various factors. Traditional detection methods have inherent drawbacks, including time-consuming processes, labour-intensive efforts, and the need for specialised expertise. Overcoming these limitations and developing improved approaches is crucial.

Deep learning, particularly hybrid vision transformers (ViTs), has emerged as a promising non-invasive plant disease identification solution. Despite advancements, accurate classification remains complex. The intricate nature of plant diseases and variations in symptoms across species and environmental conditions are significant obstacles.

This study focuses on harnessing cutting-edge classification algorithms, specifically a hybrid ViT framework for plant disease identification. Combining convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and ViTs enhances accuracy and efficiency, improving agricultural practices.

To evaluate the proposed method, a multispectral dataset was collected outdoors using lens filters, covering visible and Near-infrared (NIR) ranges. This comprehensive dataset was photographed on outdoor plants with a complex background such that good *in-the-wild* performance and thorough analysis of plant diseases is possible in a real-world setting. Experimental findings demonstrate the superiority of cutting-edge hybrid ViT models with an accuracy of 88.86%. These outcomes underscore the substantial potential of hybrid ViT models in accurately identifying plant diseases, even in previously unseen images captured under varying environmental conditions.

Keywords: Computer Vision, Deep Learning, Transformer, CNN, Multispectral

1 Introduction

Agriculture plays a vital role in the global economy as a significant source of employment, income, and exports for many countries, with developing nations relying heavily on agriculture, which accounts for over half of their workforce [Brown and Mazibuko, 2023]. Moreover, agriculture is the primary global food source, ensuring food security and stabilizing prices.

However, the agricultural sector faces numerous threats that can significantly reduce crop yields, leading to substantial production losses and financial hardships for farmers. Among these threats, plant diseases emerge as a prominent challenge, capable of severely impacting harvest production. Plant diseases encompass various conditions and abnormal growth patterns that adversely affect the health and vitality of plants. Factors such as fungi, bacteria, viruses, parasites, and environmental stressors contribute to the prevalence of these diseases, affecting all plant components, including roots, stems, leaves, and fruit [Walton, 1997].

Timely identification of diseases is crucial to minimize crop yield reductions, mitigate food shortages, and prevent escalating food prices that contribute to hunger and malnutrition. Conventional disease management

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often relies on increased pesticide usage, incurring high costs and leading to negative environmental consequences like water pollution and harm to wildlife. Consequently, plant diseases significantly adversely impact the global economy, hindering crop yields, reducing farmer income, and limiting food accessibility.

To address these challenges, effective disease management strategies must focus on early disease identification to protect plants and their surroundings. Deep learning models have gained recognition for their effectiveness in detecting plant diseases at their early stages, leading to improved disease management outcomes. This paper combines the state-of-the-art vision transformer models with CNNs to identify plant diseases during their early development.

The approach involves capturing photographs using multiple filters obtained from Kolari Vision under diverse weather and lighting conditions. These specialised filters are meticulously designed to capture specific segments of the near-infrared (NIR) spectrum, which proves invaluable for imaging and analysis purposes. The NIR spectrum spans wavelengths ranging from approximately 700-2500 nm, occupying the region between the visible and mid-infrared ranges of the electromagnetic spectrum. By leveraging NIR radiation, which lies beyond the visible spectrum, this imaging methodology reveals critical details imperceptible to the human eye, offering exceptional computer vision possibilities for various agricultural applications.

Following contributions were made in this paper.

- Acquisition of a [new multispectral dataset](#) using four Kolari vision lenses (BlueIR, K590, K850, and Hot Mirror) in diverse natural environmental settings with varying weather conditions.
- Review of multiple hybrid models combining state-of-the-art ViT and CNN models with the multispectral dataset to identify the most effective combination for early plant disease detection.
- Utilisation of two different augmentation mechanisms to assess the impact of small and medium augmentations on early plant disease detection with the new dataset.
- Comparative analysis of multiple lenses to determine their suitability for early plant disease identification research in terms of imaging techniques.
- Results comparison on multiple CNN and ViT models with the hybrid models using the same dataset to select the most suitable deep learning model for early disease identification research.

The remaining sections of this paper are organised: Section 2 provides a review of the relevant literature, Section 3 describes the materials and methodology employed, Section 4 presents the experimental results, and finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with a discussion of the results and future directions.

2 Related Works

Many deep learning approaches have gained popularity in plant disease detection research as non-invasive methods. The following review highlights state-of-the-art studies in the context of plant disease detection.

[Li and Li, 2022] proposed a lightweight hybrid model for apple disease identification by combining convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and transformers. They used CNNs to extract local features and transformers to capture long-range dependencies and global context information. The proposed method achieved 98.2% accuracy on apple disease images, surpassing several existing state-of-the-art CNN and Vision Transformer (ViT) methods.

In 2022, [Lu et al., 2022] developed a hybrid model to diagnose grape leaf diseases and pests effectively. Their approach involved a pre-processing step to enhance image quality, a ghost-convolutional neural network (GCNN) for feature extraction, and a transformer-based architecture to capture long-range dependencies and global context information. The model achieved an accuracy of 98.14% on a dataset of 12615 grape leaf images, demonstrating improved performance compared to conventional CNN models.

[Zhou et al., 2023] introduced a method for identifying rice leaf diseases using a residual-distilled transformer (RDT) architecture. The RDT architecture combined residual learning with a transformer-based approach. The proposed method achieved an accuracy of 92

In 2023, [Öğrekçi et al., 2023] investigated the classification of sugarcane leaf diseases using deep learning methods. They compared the performance of CNN, ViT, and ViT+CNN models on a dataset of 2,521 images categorised into five classes. The ViT model outperformed the other two models, achieving accuracies of 93.34

These studies highlight the advancements in plant disease identification using hybrid ViT models. Furthermore, while previous works focused on RGB images, there is a growing interest in adding near-infrared (NIR) to the spectra to effectively capture early plant disease symptoms under varying conditions – as NIR imaging can provide additional information beyond the visible range of the electromagnetic spectrum.

3 Methodology

This section presents the experimental setup for this work, which includes data collection, augmentation, image processing, and the architectures of the deep learning models.

3.1 Data Collection

Images of plant leaves were captured, including the natural background using a Canon EOS 800D camera equipped with Kolari Vision filters, namely BlueIR, IR 590 nm, Hot Mirror, and IR K850, as shown in Figure 1. Each filter allows specific electromagnetic spectrum ranges to be captured, enabling the acquisition of relevant features [Brown and Poole, 2023]. The K590 filter captures wavelengths in 590-1000 nm, while the K850 filter allows 850-1000 nm wavelengths. The BlueIR filter captures both blue (400-500nm) and infrared (700-1000nm) ranges, while the Hot Mirror filter only allows the visible portion of the electromagnetic spectrum by blocking other wavelengths.

Figure 1: Camera lenses for filtering.

Table 1 indicates that 3016 images were captured in the morning hours (8:00-11:59 a.m.) under various weather conditions, including sunny, windy, cloudy, and rainy, with temperatures ranging from 22-37 °C. The image collection focused on five fruit plants: avocados, tomatoes, limes, passion fruit, and gooseberries. These plants are susceptible to various diseases, such as bacterial spot, mold, rust, and common viruses. Examples of the collected image samples are shown in Figure 2. Due to environmental conditions, capturing the same number of samples per species is not feasible. Thus, data augmentation is used as a mitigating factor to improve training. Each image contained at least one leaf and included the natural background.

Figure 2: Image samples of the NIR dataset.

Data augmentation is crucial in this work as the dataset is relatively small for CNNs and more so for transformer-based algorithms. Deep learning models require a large amount of data, and data augmentation

Table 1: Plant species that were captured and their sample distribution.

Plant Status	Lens Type			
	<i>K850</i>	<i>Hot Mirror</i>	<i>BlueIR</i>	<i>K590</i>
Avacado Diseased	99	77	50	37
Avacado Healthy	206	144	91	42
Lime Diseased	142	124	64	50
Lime Healthy	177	104	89	38
Tomato Diseased	111	67	35	25
Tomato Healthy	111	144	114	22
Gooseberry Diseased	23	37	14	22
Gooseberry Healthy	140	127	116	133
PassionFruit Diseased	-	21	-	-
PassionFruit Healthy	100	45	75	-

helps enhance the diversity and size of the training dataset, leading to improved model generalisation and robustness. Data augmentation creates new samples by applying various transformations or modifications to the existing data, reducing overfitting and enhancing the model’s ability to recognize patterns in unseen data.

However, it is vital to note that excessive use of augmentation may result in diminishing returns. To determine the most suitable augmentation strategy for the dataset, two different mechanisms were employed: small and medium augmentation. Small augmentations included random vertical and horizontal flipping, as well as random resizing. On the other hand, medium augmentation involved random cropping, random flipping, and colour jittering. These techniques were applied with the *ViT_r26_s32* model.

3.2 Feature Extraction and Classification

The feature extraction process is crucial for classification, as it involves identifying and extracting the most relevant and discriminative features from raw data, enabling differentiation between different classes.

This research adopts hybrid Vision Transformers (ViTs), which combine the strengths of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and transformers. CNNs excel at extracting local features from images, while transformers effectively capture long-range dependencies. The proposed approach uses CNNs for feature extraction from input images, while the ViT model focuses on the classification or recognition task [Agarwal and Dash,].

The hybrid model takes an input image and passes it through a CNN or ResNet, generating a feature map. This feature map is subsequently divided into patches, flattened, and fed into the ViT model, as shown in Figure 3. The ViT model treats these patches as a sequence of tokens and utilizes transformer blocks to encode the spatial and channel-wise relationships among the patches. Finally, the encoded sequence is processed by a linear classifier to produce the final predictions.

This paper used *ViT_r26_s32* and *ViT_r50_l32* models for classification. Then the impact of the size of the CNN model and the ViT model can be evaluated by examining the outcome of the models.

3.2.1 ViT_r26_s32

The *ViT_r26_s32* model adopts a hybrid architecture for computer vision tasks. It utilizes a ResNet-26 architecture with 26 convolutional layers for local feature extraction. The input image is divided into non-overlapping patches of size 32x32 pixels, which are then processed by the ResNet-26 backbone. To capture long-range dependencies, a Transformer-based head with eight Transformer layers is employed for global self-attention [Darvish et al., 2022].

Two variations of the *ViT_r26_s32* model were utilised: *ViT_r26_s32_smallaug*, which incorporates a small augmentation mechanism, and *ViT_r26_s32_medaug*, which employs a medium augmentation mechanism.

Figure 3: Hybrid Vision Transformer

Figure 4: Transfer Learning.

3.2.2 ViT_r50_l32

This model uses a ResNet-50 backbone for local feature extraction and a Transformer-based head for global self-attention. The ResNet-50 architecture comprises 50 convolutional layers, and the patch size used in the ViT model is 32×32 pixels. The "l" prefix indicates the large ViT model, which consists of 24 transformer layers [Garcia-Martin and Sanchez-Reillo, 2023].

The hybrid ViT models in this study were trained using transfer learning. This involves initializing the model's weights with those of a pre-trained model and fine-tuning it for a different task or domain. Figure 4 illustrates the transfer learning process. Due to the limited number of images in the dataset, the hybrid ViT models were pre-trained on the ImageNet-21k dataset, and cross-validation was not feasible from a time and dataset size perspective.

To prevent overfitting and enhance generalisation, dropout layers were implemented in the hybrid ViT models. Dropout layers randomly drop out units during training, helping to prevent the model from overfitting to the training data. The Adam optimizer was used with a batch size of 32 and an initial $1e-04$ learning rate.

Early stopping was implemented to prevent overfitting. It monitored the validation accuracy and stopped training if it did not improve for several epochs. In this case, the learning rate was reduced if the validation accuracy did not improve for 15 epochs.

The dataset was initially divided into two subsets: the training set and the testing set, with a ratio of 80:20. The training set was used to train the model. In contrast, the testing set evaluated the trained model's predictions

to test the generalisation capability of the model.

The effectiveness of the models was primarily evaluated based on accuracy, which is a reliable metric for measuring the model’s performance. Accuracy is the ratio of correct predictions to the total number of predictions made.

4 Results

The experiments in this study involved using different lenses, namely K850, K590, Blue IR, and Hot mirror lenses. Each lens was tested individually, and the following experimental setups were employed.

4.1 Experiment 1

The *ViT_r26_s32* model was trained on the datasets obtained with the above lenses. Small and medium augmentation mechanisms were applied to compare the disease identification capability of different lenses and assess the impact of augmentation on the model’s performance.

4.2 Experiment 2

Both the *ViT_r26_s32* and *ViT_r50_l32* models were trained on the datasets obtained with the above lenses. This experiment aimed to compare the disease identification capability of different lenses and evaluate the effect of model size on performance.

4.3 Results

This study used two hybrid ViT models with different augmentation mechanisms for classification. The results obtained for each model are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Experiment 1 : Accuracy (%) of *Vit_r26_s32_smallaug* and *Vit_r26_s32_medaug* models.

Lens	<i>ViT_r26_s32_smallaug</i>		<i>ViT_r26_s32_medaug</i>	
	<i>Train</i>	<i>Test</i>	<i>Train</i>	<i>Test</i>
Blue IR	91.28	85.32	91.87	83.32
K590	89.41	76.86	90.16	76.92
Hot Mirror	91.41	82.75	90.86	81.88
K850	92.23	88.17	92.83	88.86

The models trained with small augmentation demonstrated superior performance to those trained with medium augmentation. Among the lenses tested, the K850 lens exhibited the highest accuracy in both the training and testing phases for both types of augmentation.

Specifically, the model trained with small augmentation achieved a higher testing accuracy of 85.32% for the Blue IR lens, surpassing the accuracy of the model trained with medium augmentation (83.32%). However, for the K590 and K850 lenses, the model with medium augmentation showed a slightly higher testing accuracy than the model with small augmentation, although the difference was not statistically significant. It is worth noting that the K590 lens presented the most challenging classification task, consistently yielding lower accuracies across all configurations compared to the other lenses.

These findings indicate that small augmentation is an effective technique for enhancing model performance across various lenses. Small augmentation facilitates the learning of robust features that introduce less noise and variations in the data. Conversely, applying medium or larger augmentations did not yield significant improvements in model performance for the tested lenses.

Given the limited impact observed with medium augmentation, further investigation was conducted to assess the influence of model size by comparing the *ViT_r26_s32* and *ViT_r50_l32* models using small augmented data during training.

Table 3: Experiment 2 : Accuracy (%) of *ViT_r26_s32* and *ViT_r50_l32* models.

Lens	<i>ViT_r26_s32</i>		<i>ViT_r50_l32</i>	
	Train	Test	Train	Test
Blue IR	91.28	85.32	92.42	84.87
K590	90.74	76.86	90.45	76.09
Hot Mirror	91.41	82.75	91.35	80.83
K850	92.23	88.17	91.73	87.28

Table 3 provides a comparison of the results, revealing that the models trained with the *ViT_r26_s32* architecture consistently exhibited higher accuracy scores for both training and testing across all lenses when compared to the models trained with the *ViT_r50_l32* architecture. Notably, the K850 lens consistently achieved the highest accuracy scores across all configurations in both models, while the K590 lens proved to be the most challenging to classify, displaying the lowest accuracies.

The inferior performance of the *ViT_r50_l32* model may be attributed to its larger size, characterised by more parameters and layers. This increased complexity presents challenges in training and optimisation, resulting in lower accuracy scores. Additionally, the larger model is more prone to overfitting the training data, leading to diminished generalisation performance on the test data. It is plausible that the smaller *ViT_r26_s32* model, with its optimal capacity, effectively learns the necessary features for accurate classification, rendering the larger model unnecessary and providing no additional benefits.

It is worth noting that previous studies [De Silva and Brown, 2023a, De Silva and Brown, 2023b] have explored the analysis with similar lens filters and experimental setups. DenseNet121 yielded the lowest test accuracy (76.69%), while the ViT-B16 model achieved the highest test accuracy by 10%. The study attributed this outcome to adverse weather conditions, such as rain and minimal sunlight, which affected CNNs more negatively than vision transformers. In particular, images containing water drops on leaves could have posed challenges for the CNN models in accurately classifying healthy and diseased plants. The collected dataset for this paper did not collect images when leaves were wet, but the results were similar – hybrid models outperformed CNNs and, to a lesser extent, vision transformers. The consistency of inference run on unseen data and the additional improvements from hybrid ViT models thus provide promising prospects for deploying it in agricultural systems.

5 Conclusion

This study aimed to address the challenges of precise identification and early detection of plant diseases by applying deep learning techniques, specifically hybrid vision transformers (ViTs) combined with convolutional neural networks (CNNs).

Section 1 showed notable contributions to a [new multispectral dataset](#) encompassing diverse natural environmental settings and weather conditions, including the plant and the naturally complex background. This dataset provides a valuable resource for future research in early plant disease detection and imaging techniques. Moreover, evaluating multiple hybrid models and augmentation mechanisms provides a results contribution to help establish practical approaches for early plant disease identification.

The experimental findings demonstrated the superiority of hybrid ViT models, particularly the *ViT_r26_s32* architecture, with state-of-the-art performance in accurately identifying plant diseases. Notably, the K850 lens dataset exhibited remarkable training accuracy of 92.83% and testing accuracy of 88.86%. These outcomes

underscore the substantial potential of hybrid ViT models in early disease detection, even in previously unseen images captured under varying environmental conditions.

The potential impact of advanced plant disease identification techniques on precision agriculture and crop management is substantial. Timely and accurate disease diagnosis, enabled by applying deep learning models, can significantly improve agricultural practices, disease prevention strategies and ultimately optimize crop yield. By minimizing production losses, reducing reliance on pesticides, and promoting sustainable farming practices, these advancements contribute to food security, economic stability, and environmental preservation.

In conclusion, this study highlights the effectiveness of hybrid ViT models and their potential in early plant disease detection. Future research can build upon these findings by identifying diseases at their earliest stages, expanding the dataset size, and refining the deep learning models. These advancements will enhance the practical application of plant disease identification techniques, benefiting farmers, researchers, and the wider agricultural community.

References

- [Agarwal and Dash,] Agarwal, S. and Dash, R. Conv-vit-hgr: A transformer based hybrid model for hand gesture recognition in complex background. *Available at SSRN 4084524*.
- [Brown and Mazibuko, 2023] Brown, D. and Mazibuko, S. (2023). Efficient plant disease detection and classification for android. *Inventive Systems and Control. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, 672.
- [Brown and Poole, 2023] Brown, D. and Poole, L. (2023). Enhanced plant species and early water stress detection using visible and near-infrared spectra. *Computational Vision and Bio-Inspired Computing. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, 1439.
- [Darvish et al., 2022] Darvish, M., Pouramini, M., and Bahador, H. (2022). Towards fine-grained image classification with generative adversarial networks and facial landmark detection. In *2022 International Conference on Machine Vision and Image Processing (MVIP)*, pages 1–6. IEEE.
- [De Silva and Brown, 2023a] De Silva, M. and Brown, D. (2023a). Plant disease detection using multispectral imaging. *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, In Press*, (1).
- [De Silva and Brown, 2023b] De Silva, M. and Brown, D. (2023b). Plant disease detection using vision transformers on multispectral natural environment images. In *2023 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, Computing and Data Communication Systems (icABCD), In Press*. IEEE.
- [Garcia-Martin and Sanchez-Reillo, 2023] Garcia-Martin, R. and Sanchez-Reillo, R. (2023). Vision transformers for vein biometric recognition. *IEEE Access*, 11:22060–22080.
- [Li and Li, 2022] Li, X. and Li, S. (2022). Transformer help CNN see better: A lightweight hybrid apple disease identification model based on transformers. *Agriculture*, 12(6):884.
- [Lu et al., 2022] Lu, X., Yang, R., Zhou, J., Jiao, J., Liu, F., Liu, Y., Su, B., and Gu, P. (2022). A hybrid model of ghost-convolution enlightened transformer for effective diagnosis of grape leaf disease and pest. *Journal of King Saud University-Computer and Information Sciences*, 34(5):1755–1767.
- [Öğrekçi et al., 2023] Öğrekçi, S., Ünal, Y., and Dudak, M. N. (2023). A comparative study of vision transformers and convolutional neural networks: sugarcane leaf diseases identification. *European Food Research and Technology*, pages 1–11.
- [Walton, 1997] Walton, J. D. (1997). 13 biochemical plant pathology. *Plant biochemistry*, page 487.
- [Zhou et al., 2023] Zhou, C., Zhong, Y., Zhou, S., Song, J., and Xiang, W. (2023). Rice leaf disease identification by residual-distilled transformer. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 121:106020.